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- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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MUNDARIJA

“Zavur kollektor suvlarining kimyoviy tarkibi tahlili va ularni tozalash zarurati (Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi misolida)”.....	20
Kungiratbay Sharipov, Ma‘ruf Nurmanov	
Forming demand and stimulating sales in Uzbekistan.....	26
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
Членство в ВТО как драйвер развития: взгляд Узбекистана через призму опыта Вьетнама и Казахстана.....	30
Ж.Я.Нуриллаев	
Mamlakatimizda tizimli ahamiyatga molik banklarni aniqlash tartibi va ularning bank tizimi moliyaviy barqarorligiga ta’siri tahlili.....	37
Xolmamatov Farhodjon Kubaevich	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida aholi bandligini ta’minlashdagi dolzarb masalalar	44
Ibragimov Elmurod Gulboynor o‘g‘li	
O‘zbekiston respublikasida elektr energiyasi ta’minoti hajmini yalpi ichki mahsulot hajmiga ta’sirini ekonometrik tahlil qilish.....	48
Fayziyev Rabim Alikulovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida tijorat banklarining xizmat turlarini takomillashtirish amaliyoti	60
Umurzoqova Adiba Ochilovna	
Qishloq xo‘jaligi kooperativi boshqaruv tizimida buxgalteriya hisobini tashkil qilishning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari	67
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
O‘zbekistonda qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlari umumiy hajmini prognozlashda ekonometrik modellar (yillik)	72
Qodirov Farxod Amirovich, Bo‘ribaeva Qundiz Muratbaevna	
Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari xavfsizligi tizimini takomillashtirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari.....	77
Mahamatova Maftuna	
Xufiyona va yashirin iqtisodiyotning amaliy tahlili o‘zbekiston miqyosida.....	83
Koshanov Abdimurat Azat uli	
Soliq tizimini barqarorligini belgilovchi omillar tahlili.....	87
Nurillayev Jasurbek Davronbekovich	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromad manbalarini mustahkamlash omillari.....	92
Soatova Nodira Boboxanovna	
Bank infratuzilmasining raqamli transformatsiyasi va resurslar bazasi shakllanishi: nazariy asoslar va texnologik yondashuvlar.....	97
Raxmatov Azizjon Jaloliddinovich, Jumayev Muzaffar Mahmud o‘g‘li	
Ichki auditning transformatsion potentsiali: tahliliy amallarni takomillashtirish orqali samaradorlikni oshirish.....	102
Misirov Akbarali Pardaboyevich, Ismoilov Asadbek Abdusamat o‘g‘li	
Xorijiy mamlakatlarda yashil moliyalashtirishni rivojlantirish yo‘llari.....	110
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	
Yashil moliya – iqtisodiy rivojlanish mexanizmi sifatida	117
Nodir Xidirov G‘iyosaliyevich	
Xo‘jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning likvidiligi va moliyaviy barqarorligini ta’minlashning xorij tajribasi va uning amaliy ahamiyati	122
Bauyetdinov M.J.	
Теоретические подходы к определениям агрессий социально - экономической и политической стабильности государства как фактор повышения рекреационных потребностей	128
Алимова Райхона Баходировна	
Innovatsion ta’lim texnologiyalari asosida talabalarning metodik tayyorgarligini shakllantirish.....	139
Komilov Umidjon Normurod o‘g‘li, Tulyaganova Gulnoza Olimjon qizi	

Kichik biznes subyektlarini moliyalashtirish manbalari	143
Nematulloev Suxrob Sobirovich	
“Sibir daryolarining burilishi” loyahasining tarixiy va retrospektiv tahlili	153
Mahmudov Nosir Mahmudovich	
Sarguzasht turizmini rivojlanishi va sarguzasht turlarda turistlarning xavfsizligini ta'minlashda instruktor-gidlarning roli	159
Tilovmurodov Dostonbek Furqat o'g'li	
Scientific-theoretical foundations of the use of ict in ensuring management efficiency and security in enterprises	165
Khalilov Bekzod Akhmatovich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit riskini boshqarish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	171
Mirtursunova Dinara Anvarovna	
O'zbekiston respublikasi tijorat banklarida masofaviy bank xizmatlarini joriy etishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	175
Tangriyev Izzat Raxmatullayevich	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida eko va etno turizmni rivojlantirishning istiqbollari va iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	181
Erkayeva Barno, Xushvaqto'v Ramziddin	
O'zbekiston bank tizimida raqamli valyutalar va yashil investitsiyalar integratsiyasini takomillashtirish	186
Nodirov Azizxon Asrorovich	
Global energiya noaniqligining o'zgaruvchanligi ekonomertik modellari	192
Be'zod Qo'ziboev	
Экоцифра: цифровизация МСП для зеленого устойчивого роста	197
С.С. Убаева	
Qishloq xo'jaligini barqaror rivojlantirish va ekologik toza hududni yo'lga qo'yishning ahamiyati	201
Ergashov Ulug'bek Zoxidjonovich	
Statistika fanining shakllanish bosqichlari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari.....	206
Nabixodjaev Abbas Abdupattahovich, Umarova Mukaddas Abbasovna	
Hududlarning atmosferaga chiqaradigan zararli chiqindilar miqdorini sanoat mahsulotiga nisbati bo'yicha tahlili	210
Baqoyev Husan Nuriddinovich	
Qayta tiklanadigan vodorod narxlari strategiyasini o'rganish: xarajat noaniqliklarini bartaraf etish	216
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanakulovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligini “yashil” iqtisodiyot asosida rivojlantirishga o'tishning zarurligi va mohiyati	221
Yoldoshev Mutalib Ibrohimovich	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda “yashil investitsiyalar” dan foydalanishning xorij tajribalari	225
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna, Rustamova Nasiba Arslanovna	
Ijtimoiy iqtisodiy ehtiyojlar va ularning iqtisodiy rivojlanishdagi o'rni.....	230
Raxmonova Feruza Musaqulovna	
Oliy ta'lim xizmatlarini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotda tutgan o'rni.....	234
Mirzaxajeva Shaxzoda Shuxratovna	
Tijorat banklari muammoli kreditlarining likvidlikka ta'siri.....	240
Karshiyev Adham Anvarovich	
Kichik firmalarning raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning nazariy metodologik jihatlari.....	245
Ruzmetov Davron Ibrogimovich, Aliyev Maqsudbek Erkinovich	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning moliyaviy resurslaridan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	251
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
“Deviant xulq-atvorli o'smirlarning ijtimoiy moslashuvining psixologik xususiyatlari”	255
Saidbekova Feruza Anvarbek qizi	
Aholi daromadlarini diversifikatsiya qilishda davlat siyosatining roli va imkoniyatlari	258
Nutfullayev Shohrux Mexli o'g'li, Qurbanov Ulug'bek Erkinovich	

Анализ показателей развития зелёной химии по всему миру и в узбекистане за последние десять лет.....	262
Фозилова Фирангиза Комиловна	
Tijorat banklarining o'zbekiston respublikasi iqtisodiyotiga ta'siri.....	270
Masharipov Rasulbek Jo'rabekovich	
Biznes birlashuvda buxgalteriya hisobi va auditni takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	273
Hamroyeva Zuhra Amiral qizi, Xayitboyeva Laylo Oybekovna, Mirzarayimov Sardorbek Ravshanovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida pul-kredit siyosatining maqsadi.....	277
Adilov Zuxriddin Marip o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarining ishlab chiqarish va bozorlararo aloqalarining statistik o'zgarish tendensiyalari.....	281
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
Iqtisodiy bilimlarni shakllanishi va rivojlanishi.....	286
Po'latov Abdulloh Xolxo'jayevich	
Теоретические основы эффективного управления финансовыми ресурсами предприятий с государственной долей (на примере узбекистана).....	291
Ахмедов Дилшод Турсункулович	
Robototexnika asoslari va maktab ta'limida qo'llanilishi.....	298
Tuxliyev Muslimbek Sherzod o'g'li	
Sun'iy intellektlar yordamida o'quvchilarni hayotiy faoliyat ko'nikmasini shakllantirishi.....	303
Mirxasilova Zulfiya Kochkarovna, Abdurahmanova Ozoda Djo'rayevna, Kurbanov Azimjon Jo'raboy o'g'li	
Levi tengsizligi uchun A.N. Kolmogorov teoremlari.....	316
Saypiddinov Shukrullo Sadrdinovich, Baxramov Rustamjon Qambarali o'g'li	
Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar bank tizimida raqamli moliyaviy texnologiyalarni joriy etish afzalliklari.....	320
Xodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich, Umedov Abdullo Umedovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasining mdh mamlakatlari bilan tashqi savdo faoliyati tahlili: o'zgarish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari.....	326
Ilyosov Asrorjon Axrorjon o'g'li, Abdullaev Alisher Maxmudovich, Tuxtasinova Muxayyo Mirzasultonovna	
Elektron tijoratni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi.....	330
Madieva Zuxra Iskandarbekovna	
Inson resurslarini o'rganishning asosiy yondashuvlari: mohiyat-ta'rifiy tahlil.....	336
Bakirov Qobiljon Mamatyusupovich	
Bandlikni ta'minlashda davlat tomonidan institutsional muhit yaratishning roli.....	340
Dilorom Tojiboyeva, Umida Ravshanovna Anvarova	
Mamlakatimizda islom moliyasini rivojlantirish maqsad va choralari.....	346
Xoliyorov Xomid Boynazarovich	
Разработка экспертной системы для оценки финансового состояния предприятия.....	352
Tajibayeva Kizlargul Ajiniyazovna	
Farg'ona vodiysi viloyatlarida kichik biznes ko'rsatkichlarining o'zgarishi: panel regressiya tahlili.....	362
Tojiyeva Muhabbatxon Mansurjon qizi	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarni hisoblashdagi asosiy muammolar va ularning yechimlari.....	368
Farmonov Ilhomjon Iqboljon o'g'li	
Xorijiy tajriba asosida korxonalar innovatsion faolligini boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	374
Hakimova Nozimaxon Sobirjon qizi	
Mahalliy davlat hokimiyati organlarida milliy kadrlar zaxirasini shakllantirish.....	380
G'aniev Elyor Sobirjonovich	
O'zbekistonda sirkulyar iqtisodiyotga o'tishning ahamiyati.....	386
Mirzayev Muzaffar Maxmudovich	
The role of international investments in greening and ecological rehabilitation of the aral sea region.....	392
Osmanova Feruza Bazarbaevna	
“Зеленое направление” совершенствования бухгалтерского учета.....	397
Ибрагимов Гайратжон Артикович	

Xarajatlarni kelib chiqish joylari va javobgarlik markazlari bo'yicha hisobga olishni takomillashtirish.....	403
Xamidova S.Ya.	
Mintaqalarni iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari va ularni takomillashtirish.....	409
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna	
O'zbekistonda kichik turar joy biznesini rivojlantirishda xorijiy tajribalar	414
Yo'ldashev Bekzodjon Sherzodjon o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida davlat maqsadli dasturlarini moliyalashtirish yuzasidan ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar.....	419
Shodiyev Shuhrat Sunnat o'g'li	
Qandolat mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	426
Azlarova Munira Muxammad-Amin qizi	
Risk management in commercial banks, methodological approaches and practical implementation	433
Baymuratova Zina Aqilbekovna, Jarilkapova Naubaxar Paraxat qizi	
The impact of competition on economic growth: evidence from uzbekistan's automotive industry.....	439
Saydaliyeva Dilrabo Baxriddin qizi	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning oliy talim xizmatlarini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni.....	444
Mirzaxadjayeva Shahzoda Shuxratovna	
Развитие производства сельскохозяйственной продукции путем развития цифровых технологий.....	450
Юсупов Мухиддин Соатович	
Tijorat banklarida loyihaviy moliyalashtirish risklarini boshqarish amaliyotini takomillashtirish.....	457
Berdiyev Akram O'ktamovich	
Iqtisodiy tarmoqlarni soliqqa tortish orqali investitsiya loyihalarini rivojlantirish.....	463
Sharipov Eldor Salohiddin o'g'li	
Iqtisodiyotda investitsiya va kredit salohiyatini bank faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	468
Ergashova Nilufar Sobirovna	
Qurilish materiallari sanoati korxonalarining raqobatbardoshlik salohiyatini boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	473
Tashmukhamedova Karima Samatovna	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishning asosiy yo'nalishlari va istiqbollari.....	479
Kurbanova Mohinur Xabib qizi	
Xalqaro sayohat lug'ati va uning shakllanishi.....	487
Abduaxadova Zilola Djamoliddinovna	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlari va uni o'zbekiston respublikasi hisob tizimini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati.....	492
Quvvatov G'olibjon Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Kooperatsiyalarning tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati.....	501
Mirzayev Musurmon Umidullayevich, Ziyadullayev Ilhom Narkobilovich	
Использование методов математического моделирования при внедрении коммерческих автоматических систем	505
Курбанова Рахима, Ахмедов Мехрожон	
Tijorat banklari kapitalidagi davlat ulushini kamaytirish yo'llari.....	511
Vasiyev Alisher Samiyevich	
Механизмы трансформации неформального сектора в официальную экономику на основе финансовых инструментов.....	515
Кошанов Абдимурат Азат ули, Муртазаев Шахрух Коньсжайлиевич	
The impact of tourism on the economy of Uzbekistan.....	519
Xaydarova Marjona, Muxamedboyeva Muxlisa, Umarov Kamron, Usmanova Aziza	
Mintaqada gastroturizm rivojlanishining iqtisodiy asoslari va zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	525
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	

Tikuv-trikotaj korxonalari brend jozibadorligini oshirishning ilmiy-nazariy jihatlari.....	535
O'rinov Akmaljon Axmadjonovich	
Bank tizimida hisobotlarni avtomatlashtirish texnologiyalari	542
Sodiqov Sanjar Saydullo o'g'li	
Engineering programs in Uzbekistan on the verge of fifth industrial revolution.....	547
Khasan Khankeldiyev	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarining boshqaruvini yaxshilashda korporativ madaniyatning ahamiyati.....	551
Akramova Nazokat Israilovna	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatining iqtisodiy taraqqiyotdagi o'rni	562
Amonov Mehridin Oromiddinovich	
O'zbekiston sanoat tarmoqlarida kooperatsiya asosida tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni mahalliyashtirish tizimini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	572
Xalilova Sevaraxon Alijon qizi	
Moliyaviy barqarorlikning asosiy ko'rsatkichlari va ularning tahlili.....	578
Urmanbekova Iroda Farxodovna	
Tijorat banklarining mamlakat iqtisodiyotida tutgan o'rnini tahlil qilish	583
Kilicheva F.B., Mengnorov A.A., Bozorova O.R.	
Bog'dorchilik tarmog'ida klasterlarni joriy qilishda yevropa tajribasini qo'llash imkoniyatlari	591
Ergashov Ulug'bek Zoxidjonovich	
To'qimachilik klasterlarini boshqarishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	598
Mansurov Saidxo'ja Kamalovich	
Barriers to tourism infrastructure development in uzbekistan: a critical analysis	605
Sarvinoz Shodmonova	
Xalqaro bozorda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari raqobatbardoshligini oshirish	609
Mengnorov Almardon Abdirahmonovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasida infratuzilma loyihalarini amalga oshirishdagi risklarni boshqarish.....	620
Yusupova Zilola Ismoiljon qizi	
Korxonaning iqtisodiy barqarorligiga erishishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari.....	626
Iminova Nargizaxon Akramovna	
Qishloq joylari maishiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasida axborot resurslaridan samarali foydalanish.....	631
Xamdamiy Eldor Toshtemirovich	
Meva-sabzavotlar eksportida transport koridorlari va vositalarini tanlash xususiyatlari.....	636
Yusupov Muxiddin Soatovich	
Рынок рабочей силы в узбекистане и ее воспроизводство	644
Шакиров Амали Улугбекович, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Деньги и их функции в экономике.....	650
Мурадиллаев Мансур Мехроживич, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Развитие сельского хозяйства в узбекистане.....	654
Махмудов Алишер Мухтарович, Камилова Наргиза Абдукахаровна	
Инвестиции и инновации в химической промышленности узбекистана: современные тенденции и перспективы.....	658
Хусаинов Равшан Рахимович, Султанходжаев Аманулла Асадуллаевич	
Tijorat banklari aktivlarini boshqarishni takomillashtirish.....	666
Mardonova Shoxsanam Bahodirovna	
Definition of agritourism as a multifunctional development in rural areas.....	672
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani ugli	
Kameral soliq tekshiruvda smart texnologiyalarini ma'lumotlarini soliq organlarining ma'lumotlar bazasida shakllanishi	680
Qurbonov Muxiddin Abdullaevich	
Проблемы регулирования государственно-частного партнерства и рекомендации по их решению (на примере безработицы в республике узбекистан).....	687
С.Э. Холмуратов	
Автоматизация аудиторских процедур с использованием искусственного интеллекта.....	692
Ходжарахманова Назира Бахтияр кизи	
Past karbonli iqtisodiyotga o'tish zaruriyati va uning omillari.....	701
Valiyev Axliddin Aroptidinovich	

Yengil sanoatda zamonaviy tikuv mashina-kichik robotlarning mexanizmlarini mukammallashtirish	705
Sirojova Muxabbat Sodiq qizi, Kurbanov Fazliddin Aminovich	
Jismoniy shaxslar daromadlarini soliqqa tortish tizimining institutsional va iqtisodiy asoslari	710
Kuzieva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Bobomuratova Manzura Panji qizi	
Foyda solig'i bo'yicha bo'nak to'lovlarni to'lash tartibi	717
Yangieva N.S.	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlik subyektlarini soliqlar vositasi qo'llab-quvvatlashning amaldagi holati	722
Turanboyev Boburjon Qodirjon o'g'li	
Motivation, goal-setting, and organizational performance: a case study from uzbekistan's chemical industry	726
Mamataliev Anvar Ergashevich, Bobur Urinov	
Применение искусственного интеллекта при организации налогового администрирования узбекистана	733
Н.А. Артиков	
Ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish zaruriyatini keltirib chiqaruvchi omillar	737
Sharofiddinova Gulnoza Iloxomjonovna	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning tijorat banklari samaradorligiga ta'siri	745
Maksudov Avazbek Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Suv tanqisligi sharoitida yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish asoslari	750
Qosimov Maxamatjon Sulaymanovich	
Rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotda raqamli va raqamli bo'lmagan korxonalar tahlili	761
Raxmonov Nodirjon Raxmonjon o'g'li	
Aholining o'rtacha umr ko'rish yoshini o'zgarishi sharoitida keksalarning ijtimoiy ta'minotiga xavflarning ortishi	767
Toyirov Shohboz Ziyodullo o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida moliyaviy nazorat samaradorligini ta'minlash ichki nazorat xizmatlari	773
Xaydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich	
Moliya bozorida xususiy banklar faolligini ta'minlash istiqbollari	777
Abduqahhorov Asilbek Ahror o'g'li	
Budjet daromadlari ijrosini ta'minlashda soliqlar hisobi va tahlilining ahamiyati	782
Abdullaev Abror Bozarboevich	
Aholi daromadini oshirish yo'llari	803
Shadmanov Baxodir Sherkulovich	
Tourism and regional identity in Uzbekistan: balancing heritage and development	808
Raximova Nilufar Aminovna, Abdukholikova Farida Erkinjon qizi	
O'zbekiston sanoat korxonalarining fond bozorida ishtiroki tahlil va muammolari	815
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
O'zbekistonda davlat-xususiy sheriklik loyihalarini moliyalashtirish va amalga oshirish tahlili	823
Karabaev Sanjar Abdusamatovich	
Globalashuv sharoitida milliy korxonalarining eksport salohiyatini boshqarish masalalari	832
Qodirov Humoyun Tolibjon o'g'li	
Бизнес-планирование и прогнозирование деятельности организации	836
Алимов Бехзоджон Наврузжонович	
Farg'ona vodiysida ekoturizm – kambag'allikka qarshi kurashning yangi imkoniyatlari	840
Soliyeva Nilufar Muxtorjon qizi	
Aholi turmush darajasi baholash bo'yicha dasturiy ta'minot ishlab chiqishda horij tajribasini o'rganish	844
Tursunov Farxod Baxodir o'g'li	
Mintaqa aholi turmush farovonligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar tasnifini ishlab chiqish	848
Xodjaniazov Shohruh Yuldashovich	
Xususiy oliy ta'lim muassasalari menejmentining nazariy jihatlar va o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	856
Karimov Ulug'bek Usmonovich	
Infratuzilma va bozor infratuzilmasi tushunchalarining nazariy tavsifi	861
G'aniyev Botir Baxtiyorovich	

Повышение инвестиционной привлекательности – важное условие повышения конкурентоспособности предприятий.....	865
Каримова Дилафруз Садирдин кизи	
Yevropa ittifoqi davlatlari tijorat banklarining soliq to'lovlarini amalga oshirish tartibi	870
Komolov Odiljon Sayfidinovich	
Boshqaruvda innovatsiyalarni hisobga olgan holda agrokorxonalarni davlat tomonidan rag'batlantirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari	878
Shaniyazova Zamira	
Практические аспекты применения статистических методов контроля качества на предприятиях.....	883
Усманов Илхом Ачилович, Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
Yashil iqtisodiyot sharoitida iqtisodiy o'sishning yangi paradigmalarini shakllantirish: nazariy asoslar va amaliy talqinlar.....	891
Alimova Guzal Abduxakimovna	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalari faoliyati samaradorlik ko'rsatkichlarining nazariy va metodologik tahlili	895
Qo'ziboyev Boxodir Azzamboy o'g'li	
Kutubxonalarda raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida biznes-modellarni ishlab chiqish.....	900
Ernaqulov Sunnatillo Nurali o'g'li	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri sug'urtalash operatsiyalari bo'yicha xarajatlarni xalqaro standartlar asosida hisob va hisobotda aks ettirish uslubiyatini takomillashtirish	905
X.A.Raximov	
Kameral soliq tekshiruvida smart texnologiyalarini ma'lumotlarini soliq organlarining ma'lumotlar bazasida shakllanishi.....	910
Ergashev Uyg'un Jabborovich	
Obligatsiya moliya bozori instrumenti sifatida, milliy obligatsiyalar bozori	916
Avezov Ibrohim Ixomovich, Yaxshiboyev Jahongir Abdualimovich	
Barqaror rivojlanish doirasida ekologik, ijtimoiy va korporativ boshqaruv (ESG) ko'rsatkichlarining yashil texnologiyalar innovatsiyasiga ta'sirini baholash.....	921
Meliqo'zieva Dilrabo Muxitdin qizi	
Yashil iqtisodiyot – barqaror taraqqiyotga olib boruvchi yo'l.....	925
Xalilova Aziza Rustamovna	
Научно-теоретические основы экономической и эколого-экономической эффективности предприятий горнодобывающей промышленности.....	930
Раматов Зафарбек Жуманиязович	
Xitoyda eksport faoliyatini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	938
D.E.Qarshiev	
Kichik sanoat zonalarida investitsion jozibadorlikni oshirishni investitsion faollikka ta'siri.....	943
Mannapova Shaxnoza Elshodovna	
Mahalla institutining samaradorligi tahlili: so'rovnoma yondashuvi	947
Bahriddinov Viqorjon Akbar o'g'li	
Формирование человеческого капитала в условиях демографических изменений: опыт и перспективы для узбекистана.....	955
Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи	
Farmasevtika kompaniyalari raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketing strategiyalaridan foydalanish yo'nalishlari	962
Вахромбек Бобоjonov	
“Hududlarda sug'urtaga bo'lgan talabning ekonometrik tahlili” bekberganova mohira ravshonbekovna	967
O'zbekiston Milliy universiteti	
O'zbekiston va xalqaro amaliyotda raqamli marketing vositalaridan foydalanish: muammolar va yechimlar	973
Uzoqova Dilnoza Yusuf qizi	
Условия эксплуатации и экологическая безопасность автотранспортной системы на основе энергосберегающих технологий	978
Мамасалиева Мукаддас Ибадуллаевна	
O'zbekiston tibbiyot muassasalarida moliyaviy resurslardan foydalanishda xorijiy tajribalarni qo'llash.....	982
Elmurodov G'ayratjon Abdumurodovich	

Buxgalteriya hisobining samaradorligini oshirish yo'llarida zamonaviy yondashuvlar va innovatsiyalar	987
Sattorov Mirjahon	
Особенности маркетинговых стратегий в условиях ограниченных ресурсов и узкой потребительской аудитории	991
Дебердиев Анвар	
DEbitorlik va kreditorlik qarzlari auditini rejalashtirish masalalari.....	995
Tulovov Erkinjon To'liqin o'g'li, Ibragimova Iroda Rashid qizi	
Инвестиционная программа узбекистана по привлечению иностранных инвестиций	1000
Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоровна, Бекмуратов Шухрат Даулетмуратович	
Turistik mahsulotni shakllantirishda turistlar hayoti xavfsizligini ta'minlash.....	1005
Rahmonov Siyovush Turob o'g'li	
Uglerodsiz energiyaga o'tishda o'zbekistonning yashil strategiya yo'l xaritasining integratsiyasi va ta'siri.....	1011
Nuraliyeva Komila Sanakulovna	
Цифровая устойчивость регионов: применение аналитики больших данных для оценки и управления экологическими рисками	1016
Маликов Шохрух Шокирович, Камалов Шухрат Камалович	
Разработка риск-ориентированной модели внутреннего контроля предприятия на этапе планирования налогов в условиях дистанционного налогового мониторинга	1024
Галеева Н.Н., Э.А.Халикова, Абдусаломова Гулчеҳра Мирзо қизи	
Анализ результатов инструментальных методов исследований у детей с врожденными пороками сердца	1029
Мухаммадиева Лола Атамуратовна	
Barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashda monetar omillardan samarali foydalanish yo'nalishlari.....	1036
Uskenbaeva Dilnoza Voxodir qizi	
Факторы повышения эффективности управления в государственном секторе.....	1043
Махмудова Севара Улугбековна	
Soliq organlari va soliq to'lovchilar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarning yangi tizimi sharoitida soliq nazorati	1048
Rajabbaeva Dildora Zakirovna, Aripova Aziza Alisherovna	
Boshqaruv jarayonlarini tashkil etishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	1053
Jo'rayeva Niginaxonim Xursand qizi	
Jahonda eksportni qo'llab-quvvatlash amaliyoti.....	1057
Xudoynazarov Sherzod Ismoilovich	
Raqamli moliyaviy texnologiyalarni korxonada darajasida joriy etish orqali moliyaviy barqarorlikka erishish strategiyasi	1063
Soibov Nozimbek Faxridin o'g'li	
Применение методов PMBOK в управлении рисками проектов	1070
Гулираъно Носирова Абдулазиз қизи	
Tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rivojlantirishda aholi farovonligining o'rni va ahamiyati	1073
Bobaev Isroiljon Abdinabievich	
Вопросы инновационных инвестиций в контексте международной экономической интеграции	1078
Шарипов Бахтиёр Михлибаевич	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari hamda tendensiyalari.....	1083
Samiyev Abdurashid Qaxramonovich, Shermuxammedov Begzodjon Usmonovich	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlar samaradorligini ta'minlash yo'llari.....	1087
Nazarov Qilich Xolmuradovich	
Improving the organizational and economic mechanisms for the development of tourism in the republic of karakalpakstan	1092
Tleumuratov Baxadir Genjemuratovich	
O'zbekistonda tumanlar barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishini ta'minlash yo'llari (Surxondaryo viloyati misolida).....	1097
Qosimova Nodira Saidovna	
Innovatsion iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishning asosi sifatida innovatsiyalar.....	1102
Azizova Maliha Farrux qizi	

Влияние инвестиций на инновационное развитие и повышение конкурентоспособности экономики узбекистана	1106
Максудова Шахзода	
Возможности снижения затрат на логистику за счет цифровых технологий.....	1112
Олимова Бахора Шухратовна	
Yashil texnologiyalar va ularning iqtisodiy tizimga ta'siri.....	1116
Sultonov Omon Juma o'g'li	
Iqtisodiy o'sishning makroiqtisodiy faktorlari va ularning ta'siri	1121
Zuvaydullaev Nematullo Oybek o'g'li	
Роль управления производством в условиях модернизации экономики.....	1125
Гулов Мухтор Очилович	
Iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining o'rni va ahamiyati	1129
To'rayev Shavkat Shuxratovich	
Роль цифрового маркетинга в продвижении туристических направлений.....	1136
Муродова Наргиза Уткировна	
Развитие финансовых рынков в странах снг: проблемы и перспективы.....	1140
Рузиев Зафар Икрамович, Каримов Ислон Ураз угли	
Современные инструменты продвижения бренда в условиях цифровой экономики.....	1145
Темирова Феруза Сагдуллаевна	
“Raqamli asrda axborot xavfsizligi: it texnologiyalar bilan xavfsizlikni ta'minlash yo'llari”	1149
Sherzod Rajabov	
Государственное регулирование инвестиционной деятельности: проблемы и направления совершенствования.....	1152
Шухрат Турсунов, Икромов Хасан Зафарович	
Economic incentives and barriers to sustainable transition in agribusiness: a comparative study of organic and conventional farming systems	1157
Mubina Toirova	
Цифровая трансформация банковской системы узбекистана: анализ внедрения fintech-решений в государственных банках	1162
Абдурахимова Дилора Каримовна	
Ta'lim muassasalaridagi ba'zi jihatlar	1167
A'zam Qutbiddin A'zam-zoda	
Klasterlar hisob siyosatida boshqaruv hisobining metodologik asoslari.....	1173
Toshpo'latov Azizbek Shermuxamadovich	
Egri soliqlarning mohiyati, genezisi va rivojlanish tendensiyalariga oid nazariy munozaralar xususida	1179
Shodiyev Olimjon Abduraxmonovich	
Ekologik mehmonhona faoliyatini rejalashtirish maqsadlari va vazifalari	1186
Abidova Dilfuza Igamberdievna	
Investitsiya loyihalarining iqtisodiy va moliyaviy samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	1200
Jo'rabekova Xumora Muzaffar qizi, Saidov Rasul Boltabayevich	
O'zbekistonda nodavlat notijorat tashkilotlarini moliyalashtirish manbalarining tahlili.....	1204
Aliyev Arslon Salom o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda turizm sohasining iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini statistik tahlil qilish.....	1213
Jumanova Zilola Tuychiyevna	
Xorijiy davlatlarda boylik solig'i va uning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	1219
Ruziyev G'anisher Usarovich	
Yer fondi va undan samarali foydalanishning nazariy asoslari (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	1225
Xoshimova Sevara Baxromovna	
Iqtisodiy-ekologik tizimlarni boshqarishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning ilmiy asoslari	1229
Kuldoshev Asliddin Tursunovich	
Влияние финтех-услуг на финансовую инклюзию в сельских регионах узбекистана.....	1236
Абдурахимова Дилора Каримовна	
Surxondaryo viloyati sanoat sohasining asosiy ko'rsatkichlari tahlili.....	1240
Kuvanchiyeva Mehriniso Davlyatgeldi qizi	
A critical evaluation of strategic management's role in promoting sustainable development in Uzbekistan	1245
Ismatova Mahliyo	

O'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlari eksportini oshirishda zamonaviy infratuzilma va texnologiyalarning integratsiyasi.....	1251
Akmal Bakhromov	
Trends and reforms of corporate governance in state-owned enterprises.....	1257
F.Djalilov	
Переоценка долгосрочных активов в нефтегазовой промышленности и определение финансового результата от переоценки.....	1269
Махкамова Саида Гайратова	
Oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari korxonalarini integratsiyalashuv jarayonlarini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirish.....	1275
Xojiev Ibroxim Ikramovich	
Sug'urta kompaniyalari moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashning muhim shartlari.....	1280
Allanazarova B.K.	
P2P lending and crowdfunding as alternative sources of financing for small business in Uzbekistan.....	1286
Abdurakhimova Dilara Karimovna	
O'zbekistonda soliq nazoratining huquqiy va tashkiliy asoslarini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	1290
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Oymatova Gulnur Mirjamolovna	
Applications of hyperbolic geometry in physics and biology.....	1295
Khaknazarova Khurshidabonu Kenjaevna, Otakulova Rukhshona Akram kizi	
O'zbekiston temir yo'llari tizimining transformatsiyasi: modernizatsiya, raqamlashtirish va qayta tuzilish yo'nalishlari.....	1301
Nasrullayev Nurbek Baxtiyarovich	
The role of tourist product diversification in sustainable tourism development.....	1305
Raxmonov Shuxrat Shavkatovich, Alimova Mashhura Toirxonovna	
Temiryo'l transporti turi tavsifi.....	1310
Shodmonbekova Nodira Kamoljon qizi	
Namangan viloyatining turizm salohiyatini rivojlantirish istiqbollari: Hududiy raqobatbardoshlik va innovatsion yondashuvlar.....	1314
Khusniddin Egamnazarov	
Kiberxavfsizlik: it infratuzilmasini himoya qilishning zamonaviy usullari.....	1321
D. Sh. Usmanbayev	
Mahalliy budjetlar daromad bazasini tahlili.....	1325
Qurbonov Nuriddin Ro'ziqulovich	
Развитие цифровых финансовых услуги в банковской системе Республики Узбекистан.....	1333
Абдурахманова Матлуба Махамдаминовна	
Avariya rejimlarida kichik yuklamali elektr ta'minoti tizimlarining kabel izolyatsiyasi monitoringini avtomatlashtirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari.....	1339
Mirzoyev Narzulla Nuriddinovich, Mamatqulov Toyir Chorshanbiyevich	
Analysis of increasing the speed of information exchange between the control interface and execution mechanisms in emergency mode in intelligent systems.....	1346
Azizbek Yusupbekov Nodirbekovich, Husniddin Esonov Mamarasul o'g'lu Assistant	
Sa'noat korxonalari va mexatron robotlarni optimal avtomatlashtirish va boshqarishda sun'iy intellektning ahamiyati.....	1351
Karabayev Ibragim Turdiyevich, Esonov Husniddin Mamarasul o'g'li, Abdullayeva Saodat Mengbayevna, Mamatqulov Toir Chorshanbiyevich	
Korxonaning moliyaviy holatini baholashda zamonaviy tahlil uslublarining qo'llanilishi.....	1355
Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna, Suleymanova Asel Armanovna	
Xizmat ko'satish sohasida xotin-qizlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlar va raqamli texnologiyalarning ahamiyati.....	1360
Mirzayeva Shirin Nodirovna	
Rekreatsiya turizmi va sog'lomlashtirish xizmatlari integratsiyasi.....	1365
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatini rivojlantirishda ba'zi iqtisodiy yondashuvlarning nazariy jihatlari.....	1369
Iskandarova D.B.	
Yashil (eko) investitsiyalarni tijorat banklari orqali moliyalashtirish.....	1373
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna	

Improvement of inventory accounting audit based on international standards	1378
Ovlayev Suhrob Temur o'g'li, Yo'lchiyev Oybek Ulug'bek o'g'li, Normo'minova Dilorom Umar qizi, Avlayeva Oybachin Olim qizi	
Artificial intelligence systems for assessing creditworthiness	1382
Mardonova Durdona Yaxshiboy qizi	
B2B bozorini rivojlantirishda raqamli marketing texnologiyalaridan foydalanishni takomillashtirish	1387
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich	
Tech-driven growth and the economy of the future: brics-t in the society 5.0 paradigm	1395
Kaldibayev Nurlan Alimjanovich, Sagdullayeva Gulnora Botirovna, Durmanov, Akmal Shaimardanovich	
O'zbekistonda tabiiy resuslardan olinadigan rentaning yaimdagi ulushiga tanlab olingan o'zgaruvchilar ta'siri tahlili	1404
Tursunov Husnidin, Ibragimov Hasan	
O'zbekistonda fond bozorini tartibga solish	1412
Sultonov Sherali Nuraliyevich	
Public perception of the feasibility of introducing islamic banking in Uzbekistan: a consumer perspective	1418
Dr. Shamirova Surayyo Kabildjanovna	
Directions for implementing the innovative digital technologies in tourism	1425
Norchaev Asatullo Norbutaevich	

DIRECTIONS FOR IMPLEMENTING THE INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TOURISM

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Abstract: The research article contains recommendations to introduce digital innovative technologies in tourism in Uzbekistan in order to improve the quality of services, to determine strategic directions for improving infrastructure and to develop tourism infrastructure.

Key words: digital economy, innovation, tourism, service, technology, hotel.

Annotatsiya: Tadqiqot maqolasida xizmatlar sifatini oshirish, infratuzilmani takomillashtirish va turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning strategik yo'nalishlarini belgilash maqsadida O'zbekistonda raqamli innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, innovatsiyalar, turizm, xizmat ko'rsatish, texnologiya, mehmonxona.

Аннотация: В исследовательской статье даны рекомендации по внедрению цифровых инновационных технологий в сфере туризма в Узбекистане с целью повышения качества услуг, определения стратегических направлений совершенствования инфраструктуры и развития туристической инфраструктуры.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, инновации, туризм, сервис, технологии, гостиница.

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the reforms implemented in our country in recent years, there are issues that require special attention. Similarly, the American programmer Nicholas Negroponte coined the term «digital economy» in 1995. This term is currently used by politicians, economists, journalists, businessmen - almost everyone around the world.

In this regard, great work is being done in the country to develop modern information and communication technologies, to create an integrated system of providing electronic state services, and to introduce new mechanisms for communication between state bodies and the population. In order to achieve this goal, a document has been adopted that provides for implementing the Presidential Decree of February 19, 2018 «On measures to further improve the field of information technologies and communications», as well as developing the digital economy, implementing modern information technologies in the country, and providing information security [1]. As a consistent continuation of economic reforms, the Presidential Decree «On measures to develop the digital economy in the Country of Uzbekistan»[2] and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers at 31st August, 2018, «Additional measures on the introduction and further development of the digital economy in the Country of Uzbekistan», which defines the goals and objectives of the digital economy about events being decided [3]. According to the implementation of this decision and decrees, the following are the most important tasks for the further development of the digital economy:

To implement and develop activities in the field of crypto-asset circulation, including mining, smart contract, consulting, issuance, exchange, storage, distribution, management, insurance, crowd-funding (collective financing), as well as blockchain technologies, in order to diversify investment and entrepreneurship.

To provide training of qualified personnel with practical work skills in the field of production and use of blockchain technologies.

To ensure close cooperation of state bodies and business entities in the field of introducing innovative ideas, technologies and developments for the further development of the digital economy.

To develop comprehensive cooperation with international and foreign organizations in the field of cryptocurrency activities and blockchain technologies, and attracting highly qualified foreign experts working in the field of production.

To create a legal framework for the introduction of blockchain technologies, taking into account foreign experience.

Our tasks are based on tourism development and service provision and the development of development directions, the question of learning what the main attention is focused on in the introduction of innovative technologies to the tourism infrastructure remains relevant.

One of the main goals of our research is to determine the directions that are considered an important factor in achieving the competitiveness of our country through the use of innovative digital technologies in tourism. This research work is dedicated to the methodology of introducing innovative technologies into the service sector, which are extremely relevant in turning the tourism sector into one of the leading sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

In recent years, a number of scientific works have been carried out on the transition to the digital economy and the application of the digital economy in the country in which the implementation of the digital economy has been interpreted and defined in different ways, but each of them will be taken a focus on the consumer as the main place. We emphasize the feasibility of relying on these conclusions, analyze the opinions and opinions of some authors, summarize their results, and briefly state our opinions on improvement.

The formation and implementation of the digital economy in the service sector is a complex process that depends on many factors. Don Topscott, Alex Topscott [4] Paul Vigna, Michael Casey [5] have different understandings on the application of digital innovative technologies in the economy, developing the theoretical aspects of these processes and putting them into practice. Carmen Babaita, Gabriela Sipos, Andreia Ispas and Andrea Nagu describe the topics of leadership style and culture for innovation in hotel industry on the leading role of innovative technologies in the development of tourism infrastructure in the field of tourism [6]. Arturo Cuenllas has published a work so-called «Innovation in hospitality management» in which he conducted research on achieving efficiency by applying innovative management methods in hotels [7]. The authors may not have paid enough attention to the processes of applying innovative technologies in the implementation of the considered factors.

Among the scientists of our country, S. Gulyamov [8], T. Shadiev [9], Y. Abdullaev, B. Berkinov [10], K. Abdurahmanov [11] made a great contribution to the application and implementation of digital and information technologies, innovations in the economy.

It should be noted that there is currently no single understanding among many authors regarding the development and formation of the networks that make up the infrastructure of service networks (tourism) and the introduction of digital economy (innovations) into the field. In our opinion, the scope of research that needs to be carried out in this regard is wide, and we should take into account the well-defined international experience in order to ensure the development of networks in proportion to each other.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology has been used to take the innovative changes expected for the coming years into account in order to determine the development of the digital economy in the tourism development and thereby studying the development of tourism as a whole infrastructure. In this regard, it has been studied the opinions of experts, a method of determining the directions of development of the components of tourism infrastructure is proposed through methods such as observation, comparison, empirical research, systematic and comparative analysis, and expert evaluation.

The research method has been used regarding the priority tasks of the tourism development directions of our country until 2025, and then concrete recommendations have been developed regarding the improvement of tourism in our country.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

At present, there is no general concept of the digital economy in the world, as well as a clear definition of the digital economy in the service sector. However, many definitions have been given. Digital economy includes various productions based on the use of the results of process analysis and the processing of large volumes of data, technologies, equipment, goods and services that allow to significantly increase the efficiency of storage, sale and delivery, and information in digital form is an economic activity that is considered the main factor of production.

It can be concluded that the digital economy is not a separate type of activity. Basically, it means entrepreneurship, business, industrial facilities, services as well. The term «digital» refers to the active use of innovative information technologies in all these areas. If the basis of material goods is considered a resource in the traditional economy, it will be processed and transmitted information in the digital economy. After their analysis, a proper management solution is developed.

In Uzbekistan, the term «digital economy» has been used in our national legislation for recent years. How the digital economy is developing in our country, according to the conclusion of separate researchers in this regard, telegram bots are actively used in our country. Various online stores and electronic payment systems are actively developing. Our citizens believe in electronic transactions as well. Until now, users have been making small transactions that do not require large costs, and are not very willing to increase the average purchase volume. In the near future, major contracts are to support the development of financial transactions through digital technologies.

The benefits of using the digital economy in the service sector are as follows:

1. Costs for purchasing tourist services are reduced (for example, advance hotel reservations, air tickets).
2. Get more and faster information about tourist services (tour packages).
3. In the digital world, tourism services have great opportunities to enter the global market.
4. Tour itineraries and services are rapidly improved by receiving feedback (tourist' opinion) quickly.
5. Service will be faster, better, more convenient.

In this regard, all work has started in all developed countries 10-15 years ago, and they have already begun to form it. We must not be left out of the process. Because we are among the countries that are rapidly entering globalization and integration with the world community.

To conclude from the above, the digital economy is a hybrid economy. This can be possible due to the development of information and communication and financial technologies, as well as the openness of the infrastructure, which provides the possibility of full interaction of all subjects of economic activity in hybrid tourism and service provision, including objects of the creation, distribution, exchange, consumption process of goods and services. For example, a tourist wants to go on a trip to a country he previously planned to visit and visits the office of a tour operator.

He sits face-to-face with him and gets acquainted with the tour packages, and if he buys the tour package he likes for cash, this is a traditional economy. Choosing a suitable tour package through the internet address of tour operators, paying money to the account of the tour operator through an electronic payment system, and receiving the tour package and tour services is called the digital economy.

This is the simplest example to explain. In fact, it is safe to say that the digital economy in tourism began in the 1980s. The reason is that from these years, tour operators began to widely use the systems of booking airline tickets and hotels through advance booking and money transfers. In fact, we are already in the digital economy, we use its conveniences, but we do not fully understand its essence.

In our opinion, the digital economy in service delivery is not a new process that needs to be developed or introduced, it means changing the existing services in a new way by introducing innovative technologies in the daily life of tourists¹. An example of this is the current changes in the world tourism industry. Turning to changes in the hotel business, social and technological changes have been observed as a result of the introduction of innovations in the hotel business in 2019-2023, and as hotels with large and well-known brands take the initiative, there are great opportunities for them.

This determines the main directions of innovations that are expected to be used in the world hotel business. These directions include the following.

1. New payment types and fees are introduced in the hotel business. As a result, according to international experts, the price of hotel rooms will become more expensive in the US tourism market in the future.

2. Tolls will also be introduced in major US cities, New York, Chicago, and Los Angeles. Experts emphasize that when calculating travel expenses, it is necessary to take into account fees, just in case. Because it is estimated that there is still time to achieve full transparency in this area. According to experts, there is also a

¹ The author's definition of the digital economy in tourism

good side to this, as opposed to increasing the price of the rooms, it is envisaged that the city taxes will not be charged for staying in the hotels with the introduced fee.

3. Innovative technologies have been used in numbers. According to Edmundson, manager of a chain of the famous «Marriott» hotel chain, in the near future in the hotel business, «internet items» - investments focused on connecting devices such as «Nest» smart thermostat or voice assistant «Alexa» will attract everyone's attention.

For example, in a hotel room developed by Marriott in collaboration with Samsung and Legrand SA, there is a growing demand for a shower that remembers the customer's favorite water temperature, wall pictures that can be changed to family photos, and a display that can show video on voice request.

For example, the introduction of new types of rooms has begun in «Marriott» hotels. They were first offered by the «W-Hotels» network. In this regard, «Hilton» presented «smart numbers». In «Smart Numbers» you can control TV, lighting, air temperature and images in digital frames using a mobile application. As a result, similar numbers appeared in major US cities and are implemented in all Hilton hotels.

As it can be seen from the above international experiences, there is a great possibility of wide implementation in the hotel industry, which is the most used direction of the digital economy in the field of service and tourism in our country.

According to the plan, construction of hotels based on innovative technologies will be carried out in Uzbekistan until 2025. By 2023, 853 new accommodation facilities (24,883 places), including 134 hotels, 232 hostels, 452 family guest houses, 3 sanatoriums and health facilities, will be established in our country, the total number of which is 5526, the number of places is 141, Delivered to 1 thousand.

Table 1. Statistical data on hotels and accommodation facilities²

The name of the key indicators		2019 y	2020 y	2021 y	2022 y	2023 y
Deployment tools	piece	2163	2789	4015	5029	5526
	room	33388	37455	47619	55277	63486
	place	71979	83115	103296	124191	144094

Thus, the number of hotels in Uzbekistan reached 1018 in 2023. The number of rooms were 33205. To achieve this result, investors who have built a newly three-star hotel with no less than 50 beds by the government and 40 million soum for each room in the hotel and Investors who build a four-star hotel with no less than 100 beds will receive 65 million for each room in the hotel is being achieved by giving subsidy.

In addition, the first 50 three-star hotels are compensated with USD 200 per room per year and the 30 four-star hotels with USD 400 per room per year.

For example, for a hotel with 100 rooms, this means 40 thousand USD per year. Such a privilege has not yet been offered anywhere. Such incentives provide the hotel industry with additional opportunities to engage in innovation.

At the same time, the adoption of international experiences in the introduction of digital innovative technologies in the development of the hotel industry will also lead to success.

Conclusions and suggestions

Summing up from the above, it is appropriate to define the following direction, which should be given special attention, first of all, considering the continuation of the work started in recent years in the use of digital innovative technologies in the formation of tourism infrastructure, they are:

-to accelerate the use of innovative technologies in terms of means of accommodation in affordable means of accommodation such as modern and brand hotels and hostels, family guest houses, as well as to implement mechanisms for providing apartments under the Airbnb system;

-to introduce modern technologies into transport logistics, development of unified, safe and innovative transport logistics, taking into account internal and external transport types that complement each other in order to increase and diversify the tourist flow;

-to create a system for tourists on cultural heritage subjects through practical information-references, implementing smart-tourism technologies, increasing the efficiency of cultural heritage subjects, museums, theaters, art galleries by installing turnstiles and video surveillance systems;

-to increase the «monetization» of tourism by establishing a flexible price policy for «monetization» of tourism, first of all, air transportation, location means services, organization of meals for tourists, cultural and entertainment events and produced souvenir products;

² Compiled by the author based on statistical indicators

- to form a countryan group to study the issues of effective application of digital innovative technologies in tourism, during the year experts of local ministries and agencies to thoroughly study the situation together with experts and representatives of the tourism sector, it is necessary to develop drafts of regulatory legal documents that reflect specific proposals for finding solutions to problems that prevent the use of innovations in tourism.

We should also be ready for the innovations and changes that are expected from the digital innovative technologies used in world tourism. Today, the competition is developing to such an extent that we need to get the right direction from the above information when developing strategic plans to overcome it.

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